

A Theorem on the Imaginary Number $\sqrt{-1}$

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$\sqrt{-1}$ is an imaginary number in the complex number system. The paper presents a theorem using the imaginary number $\sqrt{-1}$.

Theorem: $\sqrt{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}} \Rightarrow (\sqrt{-1})^n = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{-1})^n}$, where the integer $n \geq 1$.

Proof.

$\sqrt{-1}$ is an imaginary number in the complex number system [1].

$$\sqrt{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}} \Rightarrow \sqrt{-1}\sqrt{-1} = 1 \Rightarrow \sqrt{(-1) \times (-1)} = 1 \Rightarrow \sqrt{1} = 1 \Rightarrow 1 = 1.$$

OR

By multiplying the imaginary number $\sqrt{-1}$ on both sides of $\sqrt{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}}$, we get

$$\sqrt{-1}\sqrt{-1} = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\sqrt{-1}} \Rightarrow \sqrt{(-1) \times (-1)} = 1 \Rightarrow \sqrt{1} = 1 \Rightarrow 1 = 1.$$

$$(\sqrt{-1})^2 = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\sqrt{-1}} \Rightarrow \sqrt{-1}\sqrt{-1} = 1 \Rightarrow 1 = 1, \text{ i.e. } (\sqrt{-1})^2 = 1.$$

Hence, $\sqrt{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}}$ is proved.

Let $n = 3$ in $(\sqrt{-1})^n = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{-1})^n}$. Then, $(\sqrt{-1})^3 = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{-1})^3} \Rightarrow (\sqrt{-1})^6 = [(\sqrt{-1})^2]^3 = 1$,

where $(\sqrt{-1})^2 = 1$.

Hence, $(\sqrt{-1})^3 = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{-1})^3}$ is proved.

Similarly, we can prove that $(\sqrt{-1})^n = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{-1})^n}$.

$$(\sqrt{-1})^n = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{-1})^n} \Rightarrow (\sqrt{-1})^{2n} = [(\sqrt{-1})^2]^n = 1 \Rightarrow (1)^n = 1 \Rightarrow 1 = 1.$$

$$\therefore \sqrt{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}} \Rightarrow (\sqrt{-1})^n = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{-1})^n}.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

References

[1] Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Complex_number.